

Milestone: M6.1 Project Mobilised. All B1MG Governing Boards in place

Lead Participant: ELIXIR

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Due: 31 Jul 2020

Date Of Completion: 30/07/2020

Means of Verification

B1MG Kick-off [agenda](#) (04/06/2020)
B1MG-GB initial meeting [agenda](#) (29/06/2020)
B1MG-SEAB initial meeting [agenda](#) (02/07/2020)
B1MG-OG initial meeting [agenda](#) (26/06/2020)
WP Leaders have started their regular meetings with WP partners.

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

No

Project participants & others

B1MG Kick-off: GA members, 1+MG WGs and EC.
B1MG-OG: Work Package Leads, 1+MG WG Leaders and EC
B1MG-GB: Countries representatives
B1MG-SEAB: Scientific & Ethical Advisory Board members

Next action steps

B1MG-GB and B1MG-SEAB will have meetings every 6 months throughout the duration of the project or earlier if required.
B1MG-OG will meet monthly throughout the project.
Meetings with NMG will take place as part of the 1+MG WG1 meetings.
B1MG GA meeting scheduled for October 22nd and yearly.

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